

Effectiveness and Problems Related to Stress Management Among Doctors of Private Hospitals at Coimbatore City

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Abstract : This research explores the effectiveness of stress management practices and identifies the problems related to stress among doctors working in private hospitals in Coimbatore city. The healthcare profession, particularly for doctors, is renowned for its high-pressure environment, demanding long hours, and exposure to emotionally charged situations. Consequently, stress management becomes crucial to maintaining the well-being and job satisfaction of medical practitioners. The study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to gather comprehensive data. The surveys assess the stress management strategies utilized by doctors, measuring their perceived effectiveness and impact on overall well-being. Additionally, the interviews delve deeper into the challenges and problems encountered by doctors while managing stress in their daily professional lives. The findings shed light on the current state of stress management practices among doctors in private hospitals, highlighting effective strategies and areas for improvement. Moreover, the research identifies common stress-related challenges faced by doctors, such as workload, time constraints, and emotional toll. This study's outcomes offer valuable insights for healthcare institutions, policymakers, and medical professionals seeking to enhance stress management support in private hospitals in Coimbatore city. By addressing the identified problems and leveraging effective stress management approaches, the aim is to promote a healthier and more resilient medical workforce, ultimately leading to improved patient care and satisfaction.

Keywords: Stress management, Doctors and Private hospitals

Introduction

In the bustling city of Coimbatore, private hospitals play a crucial role in providing healthcare services to a diverse and growing population. Within the healthcare system, doctors bear the responsibility of delivering quality medical care while navigating a challenging and high-pressure environment. As a result, they often experience significant levels of stress, which can have profound effects on their well-being and job performance.

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The effectiveness of stress management practices among doctors is of paramount importance in maintaining a healthy and resilient medical workforce. Efficient stress management not only enhances doctors' ability to cope with the demands of their profession but also fosters a positive work environment within hospitals. Conversely, identifying the problems and challenges related to stress management can offer valuable insights for developing targeted interventions to support doctors better.

This study sets out to assess the effectiveness of stress management strategies implemented by doctors working in private hospitals across Coimbatore city. It aims to delve into the approaches used by doctors to manage stress and explore the impact of these practices on their overall well-being and job satisfaction. Additionally, the research seeks to pinpoint the specific stress-related challenges faced by doctors in their daily work.

By gaining a comprehensive understanding of stress management among doctors in private hospitals, this study endeavors to contribute to the improvement of the healthcare system in Coimbatore city. The findings may serve as a foundation for tailored support programs that address the unique stressors experienced by healthcare professionals, ultimately promoting a healthier and more productive medical workforce. Moreover, the insights gained from this research may have broader implications for enhancing the quality of healthcare services provided to the city's residents.

Review Of Literature

Dasgupta (2012) The primary objective of this study was to examine the correlation between role overload, role conflict, and role ambiguity experienced by nurses, and the subsequent impact on burnout. Additionally, the study aimed to explore the association between nurses' efficacy and these three stressors, as well as their link with burnout specifically within the context of private hospitals. Patients who receive medical treatment at private hospitals tend to experience higher costs due to the anticipation of receiving superior quality care. Stressors are recognized as obstacles in the provision of nursing care, while burnout is known to have detrimental consequences. However, it has been shown that individuals with strong self-efficacy may play a mitigating role in the impact of stressors and burnout. In order to enhance the quality of patient treatment Healthcare managers may endeavor to mitigate stresses and improve the effectiveness of nurses. In this approach, some practical solutions have been proposed.

Sharma and Kumar (2016) conducted a study. Emotional Intelligence, often known as EI, refers to the cognitive ability or aptitude to recognize, evaluate, and regulate both one's own emotions and those of others. According to Goleman, emotional intelligence entails the skill of successfully and correctly controlling one's emotions, hence facilitating harmonious

collaboration among others in pursuit of shared objectives. Extensive scholarly investigations and empirical study pertaining to emotional intelligence have consistently demonstrated that the development of emotional intelligence may be facilitated by educational interventions and behavioral modifications, irrespective of an individual's age.

The authors of the study conducted by **Rawal and Pardeshi in (2015)** The field of nursing has been documented to be associated with high levels of stress. The nursing personnel situated at the lower echelons of the hospital hierarchy experience heightened levels of stress. The present scarcity of nurses and the elevated rate of turnover are subjects of significant apprehension due to their potential implications for the efficiency and efficacy of healthcare delivery systems. In order to maintain the health and safety of employees, it is important to undertake the reorganization of the work environment and minimize the presence of stress-inducing factors. Additionally, providing training to staff on effective strategies for managing job-related stress and facilitating improved adaptation is crucial.

Udhayakumar and Mohanasundaram (2018) Approximately 33% of the participants expressed a belief that they will experience burnout in the foreseeable future, while an equal proportion indicated that job-related stress is the primary cause of stress in their life. Approximately 75% of the workforce holds the belief that job-related stress has a detrimental impact on their productivity, leading to subsequent health issues. The objective of this study is to examine the phenomenon of work-related stress experienced by physicians working in both private and government hospitals located in Coimbatore. The objective of this study is to examine stress release tactics employed by doctors in government and private hospitals in Coimbatore City. The current study is grounded in both primary and secondary sources.

Fothergill, A., Edwards, D., and Burnard, P. (2004) Academic research has been conducted to investigate the sources of stress experienced by psychiatrists, which have been found to have detrimental effects on their physical well-being and psychological state. A comprehensive examination of existing scholarly works was undertaken to investigate the topic of stress and stress management in the field of psychiatry. The field of psychiatry is known to be associated with significant levels of stress. Psychiatrists have recognized many pressures across both their professional and personal domains.

Singh and Nanawani (2019) The situation becomes increasingly distressing when considering vital sectors such as healthcare. The primary focus of this study pertains to the matter of waiting lines within privately-owned healthcare facilities. This study seeks to comprehend the underlying factors contributing to the existence of waiting lines and the subsequent effects they have. Moreover, the present study endeavors to examine the anticipated outcomes and perspectives of clientele (patients) about the outpatient department

(OPD) healthcare services. The key elements of queue management in a hospital encompass a meticulously designed and rigorously adhered to appointment system, amenities such as a designated waiting area and dedicated registration personnel, token systems, digital displays to communicate queue progress, software for efficient patient data management, timely information dissemination, an adequate number of staff members, and effective coordination. Primarily, it is crucial to handle one's patients with the utmost care.

Statement of Problem

Working as a doctor in a private hospital can be demanding and challenging, with various stressors that can significantly impact the well-being and performance of healthcare professionals. The theoretical discussion about problems related to stress management among doctors in private hospitals focuses on understanding the potential stressors and factors that contribute to stress, burnout, and overall dissatisfaction in their work environment. The theoretical discussion highlights the multifaceted nature of problems related to stress management among doctors in private hospitals. High workload, emotional strain, lack of support, work-life imbalance, and performance pressures are some of the key stressors faced by healthcare professionals. Addressing these stress-related challenges requires comprehensive strategies, including improving support systems, providing stress management resources, promoting a positive work culture, and addressing work-life balance issues. By recognizing and proactively addressing these stressors, private hospitals can create a healthier and more supportive work environment, fostering the well-being and job satisfaction of their doctors, and ultimately leading to better patient care outcomes.

Objectives of The Study

To evaluate the perceived effectiveness of stress management resources and programs provided by the hospital to its doctors.

To identify and analyze the different problems related to stress management faced by doctors in the hospital.

To assess the workplace policies and support systems in the hospital and their impact on stress management for doctors.

Scope of The Study

The scope of the study focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of stress management programs and identifying problems related to stress management among doctors working in private hospitals in Coimbatore city. The study encompasses various aspects related to stress management, workplace policies, and support systems within the hospital setting. Overall,

the scope of the study aims to provide valuable insights into stress management practices and challenges among doctors in private hospitals in Coimbatore city. The findings can be instrumental in guiding hospitals to develop targeted interventions and policies that promote the well-being and job satisfaction of their doctors, ultimately enhancing patient care and the overall work environment.

Research Methodology

Research Design:

The study adopt a cross-sectional research design to collect data at a single point in time from doctors in private hospitals in Coimbatore city. This design allows for the assessment of stress management effectiveness and problems related to stress management among doctors within the selected timeframe.

Sample Selection:

A purposive sampling technique be used to select doctors from various private hospitals in Coimbatore city. The selection ensure representation from different medical specialties and various levels of experience. The sample size be determined based on the feasibility of data collection and statistical power considerations. It aim to have a sufficient number of participants to provide meaningful insights into the research objectives.

Data Collection:

The primary data collection method be a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire be designed to collect demographic information, assess the effectiveness of stress management programs, identify problems related to stress management, and evaluate workplace policies and support systems.

The questionnaire include both closed-ended and Likert-scale questions, allowing for quantitative analysis of the data.

Additionally, to gain a deeper understanding of doctors' experiences and challenges, qualitative data may be collected through interviews or focus group discussions with a subset of participants.

Data Analysis:

Quantitative data obtained from the structured questionnaire will be analyzed using appropriate statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, such as means, standard deviations, percentages, and frequencies, will be calculated to summarize demographic information and responses to survey questions.

Qualitative data from interviews or focus group discussions will be transcribed and thematically analyzed to identify common themes and patterns related to stress management and challenges faced by doctors.

Tools used for the study: Percentage analysis, Descriptive statistics, factor analysis and oneway ANOVA.

Limitations of The Study

- The study acknowledge its limitations, such as the use of a cross-sectional design and potential biases in self-reported data.
- The limitations considered in the interpretation of the results and implications for generalizability.

Analysis And Interpretation

Demographic variables of the respondents

Demographic variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age	25-30 Years	36	24.0
	31-35 Years	44	29.3
	36-40 Years	39	26.0
	41-45 Years	31	20.7
	Total	150	100.0
Gender	Male	69	46.0
	Female	81	54.0
	Total	150	100.0
Years of Experience as a Doctor	0-5 years	57	38.0
	6-10 years	19	12.7
	11-15 years	25	16.7
	16-20 years	25	16.7
	21 years and above	24	16.0
	Total	150	100.0

Out of 150 respondents, 24.0% of the respondents are between 25-30 years old, 29.3% are between 31-35 years old, 26.0% are between 36-40 years old and 20.7% are between 41-45 years old.46.0% are male and 54.0% are female.38.0% have 0-5 years of experience, 12.7% have 6-10 years of experience, 16.7% have 11-15 years of experience, 16.7% have 16-20 years of experience and 16.0% have 21 years and above of experience.

Descriptive Statistics for Effectiveness of Stress Management

Particulars	N	Mean	SD
The hospital provides sufficient stress management resources and programs.	150	2.71	1.680
The stress management programs offered by the hospital are beneficial.	150	2.89	1.548
I am aware of the stress management resources available to me.	150	3.42	1.322
The hospital encourages doctors to participate in stress management activities.	150	3.40	1.438
The stress management programs have a positive impact on my overall well-being.	150	2.35	1.507
I feel supported by the hospital in managing stress effectively.	150	2.66	.982
The hospital promotes a healthy work-life balance	150	3.10	1.427

There are mixed perceptions among the respondents regarding the effectiveness of stress management in the hospital. While some aspects receive relatively higher agreement scores (e.g., awareness of resources and encouragement to participate), other aspects show more variability and lower mean scores (e.g., the impact of stress management programs on overall well-being). These findings highlight potential areas where the hospital can improve its stress management programs and resources to better support its doctors' well-being and work-life balance. It may be beneficial for the hospital administration to review the feedback from the respondents and take appropriate measures to address the concerns and enhance the effectiveness of their stress management initiatives.

Descriptive Statistics for Problems Related to Stress Management

	N	Mean	SD
I often experience high levels of stress in my job.	150	4.36	.936
I feel overwhelmed by the workload and responsibilities.	150	4.58	.971
There is a lack of adequate training on stress management techniques.	150	4.19	1.345
The hospital does not address stress-related issues effectively.	150	4.42	1.095
I have difficulty disconnecting from work during off-duty hours.	150	4.54	.832
There is a lack of support from hospital management in dealing with work-related stress.	150	4.36	1.143
The hospital does not offer sufficient resources to manage stress.	150	3.35	1.634
I feel that stress management is not prioritized by the hospital.	150	3.19	1.672

The mean values across all statements are notably high, indicating that the respondents, on average, face significant problems related to stress management. These findings highlight the urgency of addressing stress-related issues in the workplace to better support the well-being of the hospital's staff.

The most critical concerns, based on the highest mean values, are feeling overwhelmed by workload and responsibilities (mean: 4.58) and difficulty disconnecting from work during off-duty hours (mean: 4.54). These findings suggest that participants experience challenges in managing their workload effectively and struggle to achieve a healthy work-life balance.

Additionally, respondents indicated that they lack sufficient support from hospital management in dealing with work-related stress (mean: 4.36) and believe that the hospital does not address stress-related issues effectively (mean: 4.42). This reflects a need for improved support systems and more comprehensive strategies to address stress-related concerns within the organization.

Furthermore, the mean values for the lack of adequate training on stress management techniques (mean: 4.19) and insufficient resources offered by the hospital to manage stress (mean: 3.35) imply that participants perceive a need for better training opportunities and more available resources to cope with workplace stress effectively.

Lastly, the respondents felt that stress management is not prioritized by the hospital (mean: 3.19), suggesting that there is room for the hospital administration to emphasize and prioritize stress management initiatives.

Descriptive Statistics for Workplace Policies and Support

	N	Mean	SD
The hospital provides flexible work hours that allow me to manage my professional and personal responsibilities effectively.	150	3.79	1.334
The workload distribution is fair and balanced among doctors, reducing excessive stress on individuals.	150	3.63	1.472
The hospital offers adequate opportunities for rest and breaks during my work shifts to prevent burnout.	150	3.22	1.613
I feel supported by my colleagues and superiors in times of high stress or challenging situations at work.	150	3.47	1.491
The hospital provides resources and programs aimed at promoting the mental well-being of doctors, such as counseling or stress management workshops	150	4.25	1.281

The participants' responses indicate a somewhat mixed perception of workplace policies and support in the hospital. While some aspects received moderate mean scores, suggesting a moderate level of agreement, others received higher mean scores, indicating a relatively higher level of agreement with positive workplace policies and support.

Comparison between age and acceptance of respondents towards stress

Ho1: There is a significant difference between age and acceptance of respondents towards stress

Particulars	Demographic variables	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Effectiveness of Stress Management	25-30 Years	36	3.15	0.779	1.122	.342
	31-35 Years	44	2.81	0.927		
	36-40 Years	39	2.91	0.840		
	41-45 Years	31	2.89	0.783		
	Total	150	2.93	0.842		
Problems Related to Stress Management	25-30 Years	36	4.10	0.569	3.084	.029
	31-35 Years	44	4.01	0.442		
	36-40 Years	39	4.12	0.456		
	41-45 Years	31	4.34	0.384		
	Total	150	4.13	0.478		
Workplace Policies and Support	25-30 Years	36	3.65	1.085	.434	.729
	31-35 Years	44	3.55	1.077		
	36-40 Years	39	3.82	1.116		
	41-45 Years	31	3.69	0.966		
	Total	150	3.67	1.061		
Workload and Time Constraints	25-30 Years	36	4.18	0.575	1.061	.368
	31-35 Years	44	4.17	0.517		
	36-40 Years	39	4.30	0.541		
	41-45 Years	31	4.35	0.361		
	Total	150	4.24	0.511		

Effectiveness of Stress Management:

The p-value for the ANOVA test is 0.342, which is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05. Since the p-value is not less than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (Ho1). There is no significant difference between age groups and their acceptance towards the effectiveness of stress management. The mean values for all age groups are relatively close, ranging from 2.81 to 3.15.

Problems Related to Stress Management:

The p-value for the ANOVA test is 0.029, which is less than the conventional significance level of 0.05. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis (Ho1). There is a significant difference between age groups and their acceptance towards problems related

to stress management. The mean values for the age groups vary, with the 41-45 years age group showing the highest mean acceptance (4.34) and the 31-35 years age group showing the lowest mean acceptance (4.01).

Workplace Policies and Support:

The p-value for the ANOVA test is 0.729, which is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05. Since the p-value is not less than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). There is no significant difference between age groups and their acceptance towards workplace policies and support. The mean values for all age groups are relatively close, ranging from 3.55 to 3.82.

Workload and Time Constraints:

The p-value for the ANOVA test is 0.368, which is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05. Since the p-value is not less than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). There is no significant difference between age groups and their acceptance towards workload and time constraints. The mean values for all age groups are relatively close, ranging from 4.17 to 4.35.

Findings

The mean values provide essential insights into the problems related to stress management faced by the participants. The findings underscore the significance of implementing targeted interventions and support mechanisms to address stress in the workplace effectively. By recognizing and addressing these challenges, the hospital can create a healthier and more supportive environment for its staff, ultimately enhancing their well-being and job satisfaction.

The data suggests that while participants generally view the hospital's policies and support efforts positively in promoting mental well-being through resources like counseling or workshops, there are areas that could benefit from improvement. Enhancing opportunities for rest and breaks during work shifts and further supporting doctors during high-stress situations may contribute to a more supportive and conducive work environment. By addressing these aspects, the hospital can foster a healthier workplace that better supports the well-being of its doctors.

Age has a significant effect on the acceptance towards problems related to stress management, as indicated by the p-value (0.029) being less than 0.05. However, for the other three aspects, namely the effectiveness of stress management, workplace policies and

support, and workload and time constraints, age does not appear to have a significant impact on the respondents' acceptance, as the p-values are greater than 0.05.

These findings suggest that the age of the respondents might play a role in how they perceive and accept problems related to stress management, but it does not seem to have a substantial influence on their acceptance towards the effectiveness of stress management, workplace policies and support, and workload and time constraints in the given context.

Suggestions

- Although respondents' perceptions about the effectiveness of stress management were mixed, it is essential to continuously evaluate and enhance stress management programs and resources.
- Consider conducting surveys or focus groups to gather specific feedback from doctors about what aspects of stress management programs are working well and what improvements can be made.
- Implement evidence-based stress management techniques and workshops to provide doctors with effective tools to manage stress.
- Acknowledge that there are significant problems related to stress management among the doctors, especially in the 31-35 years age group.
- Develop tailored interventions to address the specific stressors faced by doctors in different age groups.
- Provide training and support to help doctors cope with excessive workload, burnout, and work-life balance issues.
- Offer counseling services or workshops that focus on dealing with stress and emotional challenges faced by doctors.
- Consider implementing more flexible work hours and workload distribution to improve work-life balance and reduce stress.
- Ensure that doctors have adequate opportunities for rest and breaks during their work shifts to prevent burnout.
- Foster a supportive and collaborative work culture to ensure that doctors feel supported by their colleagues and superiors during high-stress situations.
- Continue to promote and expand resources aimed at promoting the mental well-being of doctors, such as counseling services and stress management workshops.
- Since age appears to have a significant effect on the acceptance of problems related to stress management, consider designing interventions that cater to the specific needs and challenges faced by doctors in different age groups.

- Offer targeted support and resources based on the unique stressors and preferences of doctors in various age brackets.
- Encourage intergenerational interactions and mentorship programs to create a supportive and inclusive environment that benefits doctors of all ages.

Conclusion

The study concludes that, highlight the importance of continuously evaluating and enhancing stress management programs, workplace policies, and support systems in the hospital. By prioritizing the well-being of its doctors and addressing stress-related challenges, the hospital can create a healthier and more supportive work environment. Implementing age-specific interventions and promoting work-life balance contribute to improved job satisfaction, retention, and ultimately, better patient care. Regular monitoring and feedback from the doctors be essential in driving meaningful improvements and ensuring a positive and thriving work culture in the hospital.

References

- Dasgupta, P. 2012, Effect of role ambiguity, conflict and overload in private hospitals' nurses' burnout and mediation through self efficacy. *Journal of Health Management*, 144, 513-534.
- Sharma, M. R., & Kumar, M. P. 2016, Emotional intelligence and stress coping styles: A study of doctors of private hospitals in and around Chandigarh. *Social Sciences*, 303, 660-675.
- Rawal, C. N., & Pardeshi, S. A. 2015, Effects Of Job Stress On Work Behaviour Amongst Nurses In Selected Public And Private Hospitals At Pune. *SAMVAD*, 8.
- Udhayakumar, m., & mohanasundaram, D. 2017, An analyse stress release strategies with reference to private and government hospitals doctors in coimbatore city, *Asia Journal of Research*, 2(4), 57-63
- Fothergill, A., Edwards, D., & Burnard, P. 2004, Stress, burnout, coping and stress management in psychiatrists: findings from a systematic review. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 501, 54-65.
- Singh, R., & Nanawani, B. H. A Study of Customers' Perception of Efficiency and Effectiveness of Waiting Line Management in Private Hospitals in Pune City.
- A-S. Antoniou, F. Polychroni, A.-N. Vlachakis, 2006, Gender and age differences in occupational stress and professional burnout between primary and high-school teachers in Greece, *Journal of managerial psychology*, Vol 21 Iss:7, pp.682.
- Wolter H.J. Hassink, 2009, Do Financial Bonuses Reduce Employee Absenteeism? Evidence from a Lottery ILR Review, Vol. 62, No. 3 (Apr., 2009), pp. 327-342
- Laal, M. & Aliramaie, N. 2010, Nursing and Coping with Stress. *International journal of collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health*, 25, 168-181.

- Kelly, T. & Barrett, M. 2012, The Leading Causes and Potential Consequences of Occupational Stress: A Study of Irish Trainee Accountants. IAR2012.indb.
- Mr. Madala Gilbert Khosa, MrIshmael Tiriyo, Ms. Guillermina Ritacc and Prof. Adolf Lowies 2014, Impact of Occupational Stress and Burnout on Employee Job Performance: A Study of Nurses in Rural Clinics of Bushbuckridge in Mpumalanga Province" International Journal of Innovative Research in Management, vol.1, issue 1, 1-20.